

BIOPOLE Newsletter

Winter 23/24

compiled by Ruta Hamilton (BAS)

Welcome to our seasonal newsletter!

We are close to entering the third year of the five year BIOPOLE programme and it is an interesting point at which to reflect on what has been achieved so far and the exciting science that is still to come. Already, we have notched up an impressive amount of fieldwork in both polar regions, using ship- and land-based infrastructure supported by NERC and our international partners. At the time of our last newsletter, I wrote of the BIOPOLE Southern Ocean Cruise 1 team getting ready for their voyage to the Weddell Sea. Three months later, and the world's media is still asking for interviews from the scientists who took part in that highly successful science cruise. Not only were their BIOPOLE science aims achieved but also, an opportunistic visit to the world's largest iceberg, A38a, captured the attention of the world's media. At the other pole, Kathryn Cook took part in the ARCWATCH expedition to capture deep copepods under the Arctic sea-ice, deploying plankton nets through holes drilled in sea-ice. Read below about their respective achievements in both scientific sampling and media outreach.

BIOPOLE also has a major role in developing the next generation of environmental scientists. Our vibrant Early Career Network is growing from strength to strength and has come up with a number of initiatives to empower this key community in our programme. In this newsletter, Chelsey Baker and Amy Swiggs report on the second 'Careers pathway session' where senior scientists are questioned about their career paths and the advice they can now give.

BIOPOLE is also keen to develop a diversity of outreach opportunities. Jen Freer talks about her experience in writing poetry about her scientific research and its value both as a way of connecting to others and in expressing her own feelings about conducting research.

Read on also to find out about how BIOPOLE scientists are finding ways to enhance how observations and models are interconnected. Further, read our feature articles on two key BIOPOLE scientists, Stephanie Rynders and Gabi Stowasser. And finally, see all the major international meetings BIOPOLE scientists have either attended or are on our radar.

Geraint Tarling (Principal Investigator)

Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI)

The BIOPOLE Southern Ocean Cruise I (including Project Members [Andrew Meijers](#), [Alexander Brearley](#), [Gabriele Stowasser](#), [Nadine Johnston](#), [Laura Taylor](#), and [Petra ten Hoopen](#)) celebrated international LGBTQIA+ STEM Day and Polar Pride Day on the 18th of November 2023 in support of LGBTQIA+ people living, working or undertaking research in the polar regions. The team wore the pride colours and flew the Pride Flag on the RRS Sir David Attenborough. To amplify the message, [Huw Griffiths](#) (BIOPOLE Member) attended the All-Party Parliament Group (APPG) on Polar Regions event on the 20th of November. A capacity crowd, including many MPs and Lords, gathered at the Houses of Parliament, London to hear speeches and personal experiences from Huw Griffiths, Jane Rumble (FCDO), Camilla Nichol (UKAHT), James Lea (University of Liverpool) and Pilvi Saarikoski (BAS), with (self-declared gay icon) the honourable James Gray, MP, leading the proceedings.

[Read more in this great guest blog](#)

Celebrating international LGBTQIA+ STEM Day and Polar Pride Day on the 18th November 2023 onboard the RRS Sir David Attenborough and the BIOPOLE Southern Ocean I Cruise (SDO33)

Members of the BIOPOLE Southern Ocean Cruise I team also celebrated International Antarctica Day on the 1st of December to mark this milestone of peace and to inspire future decisions, through the UK Polar Network's annual Antarctic Flags initiative 2023-24. This initiative pairs schools with scientists and support personnel travelling to Antarctica, who carry copies of flags designed by students to fly on the continent, returning photos and certificates to the schools upon the conclusion of their expeditions.

Flying a hand drawn flag onboard the BIOPOLE Southern Ocean I Cruise (SDO33) at Signy Island, Antarctica as part of the UKPN Antarctic Flags Initiative 2023-24

Written by [Nadine Johnston](#), [Huw Griffiths](#), and [Laura Taylor](#)

Career Pathways Session for BIOPOLE ECRs

Following on from our successful first event in January 2023, in November the BIOPOLE ECR network hosted the second event in our Careers Pathway Series, which provide an opportunity for mid- to late-career BIOPOLE members to share their career journeys and for ECRs to ask questions and advice about how they got to their current position.

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

Written by [Chelsey Baker](#) and [Amy Swiggs](#)

BIOPOLE at the North Pole

On the 2nd August 2023, I (BIOPOLE researcher [Dr Kathryn Cook](#), [University of Exeter](#)) joined the [RV Polarstern](#) in Tromsø, along with project partners [Morten Iversen](#) and [Sinhue Torres-Valdes](#) (AWI), to participate in the 9-week ArcWatch 1 (PS138) cruise to the central Arctic. The overall aim of the 50 scientists participating on the cruise was to study the physics, chemistry, and biology of the sea ice, but I was invited along to collect samples to help address BIOPOLE WP2 deliverable ‘What controls the depth at which polar copepods diapause, and their physiological rates during overwintering?’.

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

[RV Polarstern](#) through the fog

Written by [Kathryn Cook](#)

Communicating and Connecting to Our Science via Poetry

Back in 2022, I had the pleasure of attending a few poetry workshops at the British Antarctic Survey. These were hosted by the then poet-in-residence, Elizabeth Lewis-Williams. I soon learned that poetry was not only a great way to tell stories, communicate scientific research and inspire others. Poems can also help us to re-connect to our own research and the wonders of the ocean, something that is not always easy to do when the challenges it faces (and academic pressures we face) so often dominate our conversations.

[Read more on BIPOLE website](#)

Written by [Jennifer Freer](#)

BIOPOLE Sets up Modelling-Observations Working Group

The Modelling-Observations Working Group (WG) was established following the first BIOPOLE annual meeting to enhance the links between the modelling work and observational campaigns. Regular meetings between modellers at NOC and BAS had been taking place since the start of the project to ensure a synergy in modelling effort across the institutes. However, there was a clear need for an equivalent forum for the exchange of ideas and information between modellers and observationalists in the BIOPOLE community, hence the Modelling-Observations WG was formed. The WG now involves 19 members from all four work packages with representatives from NOC, BAS, CEH, and Exeter University. Meetings of the full WG currently take place approximately every 6 months, with more focussed monthly meetings targeting specific work packages or work streams.

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

Draft infographic illustrating the range of modelling and observational activities being undertaken through BIOPOLE.

Written by [Emma Young](#)

Feature on Stefanie Rynders

I'm a physical oceanographer working in the Marine Systems Modeling group at the [National Oceanography Centre](#) in Southampton. I develop models, mainly of the Arctic Ocean across different components of the system. Projects I have worked on so far range from fundamental physics to practical applications and climate scales. BIOPOLE has got me more involved in biogeochemistry and the connection between land and ocean.

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

Feature on Gabriele Stowasser

I am a Marine Ecologist working within the [Ecosystems team](#) at the [British Antarctic Survey](#) in Cambridge. Over the last 15 years I have mainly worked on the trophic relationships in polar marine ecosystems and the marine ecosystems of the British Overseas Territories. I am interested in the spatial and temporal functioning of marine food webs and use a combination of biochemical analytical methods to identify key trophic linkages in the pelagic and benthic realms of the ocean. In recent years I have also been involved in work investigating the role of zooplankton and fish in the carbon cycling of the ocean. I divide most of my time between participating in cruises and analysing samples in the laboratory here in Cambridge.

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

BIOPOLE Southern Ocean Cruise 1 Successfully Completed

[British Antarctic Survey](#) recently led the highly successful BIOPOLE Southern Ocean Cruise I (Nov-Dec 2023), which was the first ‘formal’ scientific voyage of the RRS Sir David Attenborough (SD033). Taking place over 10 days in an otherwise logistic-heavy six-week schedule, BIOPOLE I was the first funded scientific project undertaken on our new research vessel. The objectives of this cruise addressed a range of Tasks under Work Packages 1-3. It sought to understand the role that annual sea ice retreat plays in setting the conditions for the spring bloom and how this bloom acts to draw down carbon from the atmosphere and sequester it in the deep ocean. In addition, the fortuitous placement of the A23a megaberg allowed us to undertake opportunistic sampling of how the colossal chunk of the Filchner ice shelf, first calving in 1986, is modifying the physical and biogeochemical properties of the surrounding ocean as it moves northwards. This ‘encounter’ with the world’s largest iceberg and the associated drone footage also generated massive media interest across the globe.

[Read more on BIOPOLE website](#)

SD033 crew and science party at one of the sea ice stations

Written by [Andrew Meijers](#), [Nadine Johnston](#), [Laura Taylor](#), [Gabriele Stowasser](#), [Alexander Brearley](#), and [Petra ten Hoopen](#)

Upcoming Relevant Events

International MOSAiC Science Conference 2024

**26 February - 1 March 2024, Alfred Wegener
Institute, Potsdam, Germany**

For more information about the conference,
[please click here](#)

East Meets West Joint BIOPOLE-ACEAS Workshop

14-15 March 2024, Hobart, Tasmania

ICES-PICES 7th International Zooplankton Production Symposium

17-22 March 2024, Hobart, Tasmania

For more information about the symposium and to
register, [please click here](#)

2024 Ocean Decade Conference

10-12 April 2024, Barcelona, Spain

**For more information, contact Jen Freer, Amy Swiggs,
Nadine Johnston and Adrian Martin**

BIOPOLE Annual Science Meeting

**6-8 March 2024, British Antarctic Survey,
Cambridge**

Goldschmidt2024

18-23 August 2024, Chicago

For more information about the conference and to register, [please click here](#)

